

DEVELOPING COURSES IN ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES

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Abstract. *The article also highlights the reasons for the increase in the promotion of English for various fields in the modern world, as well as the fact that ESP plays an important role in society and modern methods of education in the effective teaching and learning of English.*

Keywords: *English, specific purposes, ESP, EMP, developing courses, learning English.*

INTRODUCTION: English is the language of today’s society. From the 17th century, England established dominance over many countries of the world and English began to become the language of trade over the seas so that English was recognized as the language of the world. Since English is considered the most important language for international communication, it is also growing rapidly to promote to other areas. Such as course of ESP will focus on medical professionals, business, police, scientists or economist. Because, to be able to get a good job without knowing it, to leave for a foreign country for a trip, and to communication is impossible. Not only these reasons enough to study ESP, but also it helps to expand people world view and provide access to several cultures. One of the main advantages of learning English is to enable to studying around the world. To expect, as English is spoken in many countries, programs in English are offered in a lot of educational institutions.

As international borders are becoming more accessible for working professionals, especially for experts in the healthcare field, the importance of English is also significantly increasing. English has become one of the common language of communication across nations in all scientific fields, including the field of medical science and healthcare.[1] Learning English helps to function good communication skills with colleagues or patients of other nationalities and it plays an important role in exchange of experience with overseas medics. Currently, private clinics are more increasing and as a result, cooperation with many foreign hospitals is underway. They are working on effective methods of treating patients using modern technologies.

Helen Basturkmen in “ Developing courses in English for specific purposes” highlights about the organized course to help a group of overseas-trained medical doctors who were preparing to sit medical registration examination in New Zealand. During the registration examination, the professional development trainers had noticed that a number of the overseas-trained doctors came across difficulties in conducting medical consultation and they knew their difficulties in part related to English language problems. The convener requested the course development of ESP services. The fact focuses on the development of EMP. [2] Knowledge of English is essential to business too. Learning English will be mandatory for most of its employees if an organization is focused on working with foreign partners, conducts a foreign business or has the representation of an international company.

Use of English in social media that reflects recent trends in business communication. Learning English helps based on to conduct an up-to-date research business communication and to incorporate on international range of real-world in a relation with communication in business today. [3]

A.Finn conducted a conference training in South Korea the use of English in business, a Brazilian doing business with the Dutch uses English; and an American and a German probably also employ English. Thus, most English-medium communications in business are non-native

speaker (NNS-NNS), and the English, they use International English, not that of native speakers (NS) of English-medium countries such as the UK and Australia. [4] Business demands strong communication skills. Currently, English is the dominant language of interaction with foreign company, negotiation and professional success in the workplace in business. There is more of a consensus on the key communication events of business. Some of the results of needs analysis identify seven core events: five events require primarily oral language: telephoning, socializing, marking presentations, taking part in meetings and negotiating; and two events require written form: corresponding and reporting. English is clearly expressed in these sentences.[5]

Business English skills are vital for getting ahead in your career. If working effectively in an international environment is your goal, improving your business English vocabulary and knowledge is a must. It will open many doors and bring new career opportunities. There is a wide range of English language courses available in the market. All of them can help you improve your English skills. However, business English language is a specialized part of English focused on the corporate language that is most commonly used in business world. It's part of the skill set for the international business community[6]

In the view of the fact that police officers can come into contact with foreigners within their daily duties, the authority lays emphasis on their language skills. On their duty policeman face a lot of situations when knowledge of English for specific purposes is vital. Such as, dealing with traffic checks and offences, problems at the airports or dealing with issues of immigration. As the brief insight into the scope of education suggests, ESP is taught mainly in further professional language courses and at the college. [7] Currently, tourism is developing rapidly. Police can help tourists from foreign countries, for example, police protect their rights, give directions, ask for passport for identification.

Frontline officers need precise command of a range of language specific to the police. They use this language to talk about crimes, including suspect descriptions, locations, directions, crime scenes, description of vehicles, injuries, damage and police technical terms with colleagues, with the general public and offenders. Another situation which prevents from improving the level tourist police staff English language communicative competence and performance in their work place is that they do not have support from any Government Institution in giving them seminars, workshops oriented to tourism and English language knowledge. The tourist police officers lacked the English language knowledge as much as in theory and practice, this represented an obstacle for accomplishing efficiently their jobs. [8] The aim is to promote English for the police.

The main purpose of ESP is to qualify learners with the relevant grammar, vocabulary, jargon and pronounce. Prescriptivism plays an important role in ESP. The favoured variety is usually a version of the standard written language, especially as encountered in literature, or in the formal spoken language which most closely reflects literary style, and it is presented in dictionaries, grammars and other official manuals.[9]

CONCLUSION: English for specific purposes is relevant in a particular fields and academic context. It is possible to avoid the challenges and mistakes in various ESP exams by learning English and its development has a good effect on communicative approaches. ESP helps professionals of different areas to achieve successful on their workplace.

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